

ISic3352

Antiquarian 'invented' inscription, dedication by Gorgon

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

column

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2016.05.11 (seen in store by Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Biscari (1784) states that it was found at Messina among the ruins of the earthquake in 1783; subsequent accounts in the early C19 attribute it to Capo Peloro (in Korhonen's view, a later refinement/attribution by Biscari)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 355

Physical Description

A smooth cylindrical column, with a moulding around the top and a small cavity (2cm diam) in the upper surface.

Dimensions

Height 46.5 cm

Width 21 cm

Depth 21 cm

Layout

Text in Greek letters over five lines, over the lower two thirds of the vertical side of the column

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-5: 25-30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. θεοῖς πᾶσι
2. σωτηῆρσιν
3. Γόργον
4. καὶ
5. οἱ ἄλλοι πολῖται

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

To all the deliverer Gods. Gorgon and the other citizens.

Commentary

Although originally believed by Korhonen 2004 to be an imperial Roman archaising text, Korhonen 2018 provides convincing arguments and explanations for believing this to be a later 18th century creation.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645595

PHI 316302

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0349bis (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 236

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5592 adn

Korhonen, K. 2018. Quattro iscrizioni di interesse storico-religioso attribuite a Messina. *Linguarum Varietas.* 7: 105-118. At 112-116 no.2 fig.2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3352. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358417>